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Antifungal Effect of Ethanol Extracts 70% of *Terminalia Ivorensis* and *Terminalia Superba* on two Phytopathogenic Fungi

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Abstract

Lumber is the raw material for the wood industry. Much of the bark from these logs is either buried or incinerated without any form of recovery. This study was carried out to verify the antifungal power of the trunk barks of two forest species: *Terminalia ivorensis* and *Terminalia superba*, on two fungal parasites, *Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici* and *Sclerotium rolfsii* of the tomato. They were tested in vitro using the double dilution method. Ethanol extracts from both species significantly inhibited the radial growth of both mycopathogens (100 ± 00 and 68.46 ± 5.35). *T. superba* was fungicidal at 25mg/ml against *F. oxysporum lycopersici* and *S. rolfsii*. *T. ivorensis* was fungistatic at 25mg/ml against *F. oxysporum lycopersici* and fungicidal at the same concentration against *S. rolfsii*. These barks generally contain a wide variety of raw natural products that can be a potential source of new molecules effective against phytopathogens.

Keywords : *Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Solanum lycopersicum* (L.), plant extracts, Côte d'Ivoire

1. Introduction

As far back as the history of mankind goes, Man has always used plants for their therapeutic and food-processing properties. Over the years, Man has stopped the tradition of gathering plants and has become a grower (Rocher, 2004). Thus, for his socio-economic development, he has devoted himself to agriculture. It is therefore one of the main sectors of activity that employs more than 40% of the world's working population, including more than 52% in Africa (Momagri, 2016).

In Côte d'Ivoire, agriculture is one of the pillars of economic development. In this field, market gardening, which is a highly specialised crop, is practised in all areas with high agricultural production. It appears to be one of the main components of urban and peri-urban agriculture, which is of paramount importance in the economic development of cities (FAO, 2012 cited by Boni *et al.*, 2017).

In addition, the tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is one of the most important vegetable crops in the world (Shankara Naika, 2005). It has a prominent position both nutritionally and economically. However, the production of this widely consumed commodity faces many constraints, including parasitic diseases caused by the action of various pathogens such as telluric fungi, also known as geophilic fungi, which develop at the expense of the plant (Lepoivre, 2003).

National production, which was 52,000 tons/year according to Soro (2009), remains well below the national need for tomatoes, which was estimated at over 200,000 (N'Zi *et al.*, 2010). This drop in yield caused by several factors, including the action of certain pathogens, is a real brake on food production, to the detriment of farmers who cannot afford expensive synthetic pesticides.

Among the fungal parasites encountered, it is estimated that the genus *Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici* has a large negative impact on young tomato crops (Soro *et al.*, 2008 ; Hibar *et al.*, 2007), and is among the

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most aggressive soil fungi, causing fusarium wilt and rot in many cultivated plant species. On the other hand, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, which is a soil fungus, infects a wide range of vegetable crops and harvested or stored produce, and also causes yellowing and wilting of the plant.

In spite of the damage and injury caused by these plant pathogens in crops, their control is still a challenge for the world of food crops and vegetables. In addition, the pests are resistant to the pesticides used, and pose a real health problem, not only for the users, but also for the general population. A new alternative for phytosanitary management is needed and it is plant-oriented. Thus, we were interested in the bark of two species of timber harvested in the south of Côte d'Ivoire, precisely in the Department of Tiassalé. The general objective of this study is to verify the antifungal power of the trunk barks of *Terminalia ivorensis* and *Terminalia superba* on two telluric mycopathogens of tomatoes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Plant material

It is made from the powder from the bark of the trunk, *Terminalia ivorensis* and *Terminalia superba*, two timber species of the Combretaceae family prized in the timber trade in Côte d'Ivoire. Specimens of *T. ivorensis* and *T. superba* are available at the Herbarium of the National Floristic Centre of the Felix Houphouët-Boigny University under numbers 8855 and 10477 respectively.

2.2 Fungal material

The fungal material is composed of two fungal isolates, *Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici* and *Sclerotium rolfsii*, supplied by the Phytopathological Mycotheque of the Laboratory of Plant Physiology of Felix Houphouët-Boigny University (Côte d'Ivoire).

2.3 Harvesting, drying and spraying of drugs

After the bark has been collarded, the impurities are removed, cut into small cubes and then dried at laboratory temperature (25-27°C) for three weeks. After drying, they are pulverised using an IKA® electric mill.

2.4. Preparation of crude extracts

Three extractions were performed on each fine powder, following the protocol of Zirihi and Kra (2003). Two aqueous total extracts coded X and X' were obtained, see figure 1. They were stored in sterile glass jars, hermetically sealed, in the refrigerator at +4°C.

The 70% ethanol extraction was carried out with 30 g of each total aqueous extract which was dissolved in 300 ml of 70% ethanol for one hour using a stirrer. A separating funnel was used to obtain an upper phase, 70% ethanolic, and a deposit (Zirihi et al., 2007). The 70% ethanolic phase was filtered on 3 mm Wattman® filter paper and evaporated dry under vacuum at 50°C. The 70% ethanolic extracts obtained are denoted X₀ and X₀'. Residual aqueous deposits were concentrated with Rotavapor® at 60°C and then freeze-dried. The extracts obtained are denoted X₁ and X₁', see figure 1.

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Figure 1 : Diagram of extraction of trunk bark powder using distilled water and 70% ethanol, *Terminalia ivorensis* and *Terminalia superba*.

2.5. Sterility tests of extracts

A sterility test has been carried out on the extracts to check that they are germ-free. Thus, in 10 ml of Thioglycolate broth, 100 mg of the substance to be tested were introduced. After a 24-hour incubation at 37°C, the broth was inoculated onto Mueller-Hinton agar and Sabouraud agar in Petri dishes, then the dishes were incubated under the same conditions as before. The substance is declared sterile, if no colony is visible on the agars. The plates are stored for 3 to 5 days in an oven at 37°C. If microorganisms grow, the extract is sterilised by passing it through a millipore[®] filter (HA: 0.45µm) and the test is repeated.

2.6. Production of the fungal inoculum of telluric species

A spore mass was spread on the nutrient culture medium PDA and then incubated in the dark for 24 hours at a temperature of 28°C. The germinating spore was aseptically collected under a binocular magnifying glass and transferred to another PDA medium. After two weeks incubation in the oven at 28°C, the spore produced a homogeneous clone of the fungus. 6 mm mycelial discs were prepared for use.

3. Determination of M.I.C.

3.1. Agar preparation and incorporation of extracts

This technique was applied in 90 mm Petri dishes. The PDA medium was prepared in eight Erlenmeyer flasks, numbered 0 to 7, by homogenising 11.05 g of agar in 170 ml of distilled water. This preparation is sterilised at 121°C for 15 minutes and kept under supercooled at 45°C.

All extracts have been tested separately. The number of Petri dishes for a series of tests was 8. For each series, one Petri dish without plant extract was used as a quality control witness for germ growth (T0). Each plant extract, defined by a specific mass, was emulsified and homogenised by hand stirring in the culture media quantified in the erlenmeyer flasks, just before pouring them into the Petri dishes. Each Petri dish received 20 ml of the PDA culture medium from N° 1 to N° 7.

The mixture thus poured under the hood in the presence of a flame is covered and left to stand until it cools and solidifies. An increasing concentration range of extracts from 0.39 mg/ml to 25 mg/ml with a geometric linkage of reason ½ has been achieved for each plant extract.

3.2. Cultivation of soil germs

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The inoculation of the different fungal isolates was done on the media previously prepared in Petri dishes. A 6 mm diameter mycelial disc taken from the fungus culture was inoculated in the centre of the surface of the solidified P. D.A. medium from each Petri dish. After inoculation, the Petri dishes (controls and assays) were incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 48 hours in the oven.

3.3. Measuring radial growth

After 48 hours of incubation, the radial mycelial growth was measured in millimetres on two perpendicular diameters, traced on the bottom of the Petri dish. These measurements were made every two days, just before the mycelial filaments reached the periphery of the petri dish in the control batches. When no mycelial growth was observed for a given concentration, it constituted the M.I.C. ; the lowest concentration of extract that inhibits the mycelial growth of the fungus. The determination of the minimum fungicide concentration (M.F.C.) was carried out by transplanting the mycelial disc taken in the presence of a flame into a M.I.C. Petri dish and transplanted into a new Petri dish containing PDA medium. All these plates were kept in an oven at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 48 hours.

Each extract was evaluated as fungicidal at the end of incubation, if there is no mycelial regrowth; otherwise the plant extract is declared fungistatic (Soro *et al.*, 2010; Neri *et al.*, 2006; Oxenham *et al.*, 2005).

The level of inhibition (Ti) of mycelial growth in Petri dishes by plant extracts was evaluated compared to controls according to the modified formula of Hmouni *et al* (1996) :

$$Ti (\%) = (Do - D / Do) \times 100$$

Ti : inhibition rate (%) ; Do : average diameter of control batch ; D : average diameter of test batch.

Inhibitory concentrations at 50% (IC₅₀) of mycelial growth were calculated according to the inhibition rates for each extract. The concentrations of the extracts were transformed into concentration log and the IC₅₀ were calculated after linearisation of the curves of evolution of the rates of inhibition of mycelial growth.

Lethal inhibitory concentrations were evaluated at the end of the experiment for each extract of the two plants on fungi. The lethal inhibitory concentration (L.I.C.) was determined from the lowest concentration at which no mycelial growth and no mycelial pellet recovery was observed on the PDA culture medium at the end of the experiment time (Soro *et al.*, 2010 ; Paranagama *et al.*, 2003).

The experiment was repeated 3 times over time and the results were calculated from the average of the data collected after the different observations.

3.4. Statistical analysis of the data

Data analysis was carried out using Excel (version 2007) for Windows. The results were expressed as means, standard deviations and standard differences.

4. Results

4.1. Sterility tests of extracts

No microbial colonies were observed in the different Mueller-Hinton agar and Sabouraud agar Petri dishes following sterility tests. The extracts were declared sterile.

4.2- Effects of ethanol extracts 70%.

The activity of the 70% ethanol extracts of the two *Terminalia* is very little variable. Experimental data indicate, compared to the controls, that there was a progressive decrease in the radial growth of the two telluric mycopathogens as a function of concentration (Figures 2 to 5).

Three cases of total inhibition ($100\% \pm 0.00$) were observed at a concentration of 25 mg/ml. These were ethanol extracts of *T. ivorensis* and *T. superba* on *Sclerotium rolfisii* and *T. superba* on *Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici* (Table 1). On the other hand, the ethanolic extract of *T. ivorensis* had a strong activity on *F.oxysporum lycopersici* with an inhibition rate of $68.46\% \pm 5.35$ at 25 mg/ml.

The increasing rate of inhibition of the two ethanol extracts illustrates that the extracts were active on *S. rolfisii* and *F. oxysporum lycopersici*, according to a dose-effect relationship (Figures 6 and 7). The 70% ethanolic extract of *T. ivorensis* shows a difference from concentrations of 1.56 mg/ml to 25 mg/ml in the inhibition of the two telluric strains. At this concentration range, the extract has a greater activity on *F.*

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oxysporum lycopersici compared to *S. rolfsii*. As for *T. superba*, a high sensitivity of *S. rolfsii* compared to *F. oxysporum lycopersici*, from concentrations of 1.56 mg/ml to 25 mg/ml was observed.

Reconciliation of the activity of the two ethanol extracts shows that *T. superba* appears as the most active extract with IC₅₀ of 5.88 mg/ml and 3.16 mg/ml respectively on *F. oxysporum lycopersici* and *S. rolfsii*, against the ethanolic extract of *T. ivorensis* with IC₅₀ of 16.59 mg/ml and IC₅₀ of 3.98 mg/ml respectively on *F. oxysporum lycopersici* and *S. rolfsii*.

Figure 2. Inhibitory effect of the 70% ethanolic extract of *T. superba* on the radial mycelial growth of *Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici* after eight days of incubation at 25°C.

Figure 3 Inhibitory effect of the 70% ethanolic extract of *T. superba* on the radial mycelial growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii* after eight days of incubation at 25°C

T0 : controls ; C1 : 0.39mg/ml ; C2 : 0.78 mg/ml ; C3 : 1.56 mg/ml ; C4 : 3.12 mg/ml ; C5 : 6.25 mg/ml ; C6 : 12.5 mg/ml ; C7 : 25 mg/ml

Figure 4 : Inhibitory effect of the 70% ethanolic extract of *T. ivorensis* on the radial mycelial growth of *Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici* after eight days of incubation at 25 ° C.

Figure 5 : Inhibitory effect of the 70% ethanolic extract of *T. ivorensis* on the radial mycelial growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii* after eight days of incubation at 25 ° C.

Plant species	Excerpts	Telluric fungal strains			
		<i>Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici</i>		<i>Sclerotium rolfsii</i>	
		Inhibition rate (%)	IC ₅₀ (mg/ml)	Inhibition rate (%)	CI ₅₀ (mg/ml)
<i>Terminalia ivorensis</i>	X ₀	68.46 ± 5,35	16.59	100 ± 0,00	3.98
<i>Terminalia superba</i>	X ₀ '	100 ± 0,00	5.88	100 ± 0,00	3.16

Table 1. Inhibition rate (%) and IC₅₀ (mg/ml) of ethanol extracts 70% to 25 mg/ml

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X₀ : 70% ethanolic extract of *T. ivorensis* X₀' : 70% ethanolic extract of *T. superba*

Figure 6. Inhibition rate of the 70% ethanolic extract of *T. ivorensis* on the radial mycelial growth of *Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici*

Figure 7. Inhibition rate of the 70% ethanolic extract of *T. superba* on the radial mycelial growth of *F. oxysporum lycopersici* and *S. rolfsii* after eight days of incubation at 25°C

5. Discussion

The therapeutic evaluation of the bark extracts of the two commercial plant species used against mycopathogens first required an extraction of the active ingredients. To do this, we started with the preparation of the total extracts, as water is the most common solvent used in the preparation of traditional recipes. In the quest to improve the activity of the total extracts, we made ethanol extracts as presented above.

Sensitivity tests carried out with the 2 raw ethanol extracts revealed the presence of activity on the 2 germs. This sensitivity was carried out according to a dose-effect relationship. This resulted in clear and effective inhibitions of radial mycelial growth of these fungal isolates at a maximum inhibition rate of 25 mg/ml.

Comparison of the two extracts shows that the *T. superba* extract had a clear and effective inhibitory action on the 2 phytopathogens at 25 mg/ml. On the other hand, *T. ivorensis* showed a good reduction in the radial growth of *F. oxysporum lycopersici* with an inhibition rate of 68.45% at the 25 mg/ml concentration. The results obtained confirm those of Sagitov *et al*, (2011) and Bolou *et al*, (2015) who showed *in vitro* that the

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extracts and essential oil of certain plant species would have fungicidal power respectively on strains of *F. oxysporum lycopersici* and *Sclerotium rolfsii*.

According to the work of Coulibaly (2012), the tri-phytochemical work carried out on the powder of the trunk bark of these plant species has revealed several chemical groups, namely saponosides, flavonoids, tannins, polyphenols and specifically terpenes and sterols as well as coumarins for *T. ivorensis*.

The presence of these chemical compounds in these two species could certainly justify their antifungal activities against the genera *F. o. lycopersici* and *S. rolfsii* (Kamou et al., 2016). Furthermore, despite the importance of chemical compounds in *T. ivorensis*, *T. superba* strongly inhibited both mycopathogens. This could be explained by the presence of minor compounds in addition to the compounds found to make a significant contribution to its inhibitory action (Hajji et al., 2016). The results obtained with the different concentrations of the two *Terminalia* species show that the inhibitory activity is significant but different with respect to the species tested.

6. Conclusion

This study assessed the antifungal activity of the trunk bark of two timber species, exploited in Côte d'Ivoire solely for the quality of their wood, against two tomato mycopathogens. Both species showed clear and effective inhibitions on the radial growth of the two fungi. *Terminalia superba* was fungicidal at 25 mg/ml against *Fusarium oxysporum lycopersici* and *Sclerotium rolfsii*. As for *Terminalia ivorensis*, it was fungicidal at 25 mg/ml against *F. oxysporum lycopersici* and fungicidal at the same concentration against *S. rolfsii*. The trunk bark of these two species contains several chemical groups which are responsible for their activities on these two damaging tomato fungi. This shows that ethanol extracts from the barks of *T. ivorensis* and *T. superba* are able to protect tomato crops against fusarium and sclerotia. All in all, these results are only a first step in the search for natural, inexpensive and environmentally friendly plant protection products to combat plant pathogens.

7. Acknowledgements

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